

Research Article

Assessing Community Satisfaction with the Services and Programs of General Mariano Alvarez Fire Station

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Abstract

The Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP) is a public sector that provides services to prevent and suppress destructive fires. It is responsible for the enforcement of the Fire Code of the Philippines, the Issuance of Fire Safety Evaluation Certificates and Fire Safety Inspection Certificates for every home and business owner. Unfortunately, this requires multiple stages of processes that can cause delays in issuing the government permits, and sometimes becomes the cause of destructive fires. The purpose of this study was to assess the satisfaction levels of respondents on the implementation of the BFP programs and services, as well as determining the whether the demographic characteristics of the respondents play a role in this satisfaction, and what can be learned from them. A sample of 320 respondents were randomly selected from various barangays in General Mariano Alvarez, Cavite, and a researcher-made questionnaire was used to gather the data before being statistically treated. The study concludes that the BFP successfully implements its programs and services, with consistently high satisfaction ratings among both residents and BFP personnel across various demographic groups. Enhancing disaster preparedness drills, refining business application processes at Business One-Stop Shop (BOSS), and further promoting inclusivity in emergency response efforts can help sustain and enhance public trust in the BFP. Ultimately, maintaining transparency, efficiency, and accessibility will be key to continuously improving service delivery and ensuring community safety and resilience.

Keywords: Bureau of Fire Protection, Fire Safety Inspections, Fire Safety Evaluations, Government Permits.

Introduction

The Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP) is a public sector that provides services to prevent and suppress destructive fires. It is responsible for the enforcement of the Fire Code of the Philippines (Republic Act or RA 9514). Issuance of Fire Safety Evaluation Certificates and Fire Safety Inspection Certificates for every home and business owner requires multiple stages of processes that cause delays in issuing the aforementioned government permits, and sometimes it becomes the cause of a destructive fire. Since the start of BFP Citizen's Charter implementation in March 2009, the Bureau of Fire Protection management has been thoroughly working on how to further improve the delivery of public service, especially in the field units and fire stations, not only complying with the service standards on the issuances of Fire Safety Inspection Certificate (FSIC) and Fire Safety Evaluation Clearance (FSEC) as identified priority frontline services being given by the BFP but most especially on how to improve the organization's performance in the delivery of public service.

The handbook for customer relations officers on basic customer service skills aims to strengthen the implementation of the BFP Citizens' Charter and enhance the quality of services to the public by institutionalizing courtesy and mechanisms for quick service providers to improve their skills, attitudes, and behaviors, as well as commitment to service, thereby attaining customer satisfaction. The BFP management believes in helping stations/units strengthen the organization's integrity and adapt and institutionalize service improvements that have emerged from their efforts to continually seek better ways of doing things. Community satisfaction surveys were essential tools in assessing the perceived effectiveness of public services. These surveys not only capture the community's perceptions but also highlight specific aspects of services that may need enhancement. The BFP can develop strategies to address identified gaps and improve

overall service quality by evaluating community feedback. This study aims to determine how the General Mariano Alvarez, Cavite, community perceives the effectiveness of the BFP's programs and services. Moreover, the study has explored various dimensions of BFP services, including fire safety enforcement, firefighting operations, emergency medical services, and disaster management. Each area plays a vital role in maintaining public safety and requires a thorough assessment to ensure it meets the community's needs. By analyzing community satisfaction and service quality, this study will comprehensively understand the efficiency of BFP's services and programs at General Mariano Alvarez Fire Station.

Literature Review

The workforce and organizational dynamics of fire personnel were evolving due to factors like increasing community safety needs, technological advancements, and changing demographics. Fire departments are adapting by integrating new technologies, diversifying recruitment efforts, and focusing on workforce development to maintain operational effectiveness and safety. The fire department plays a crucial role in mitigating fire incidents and their impacts on livelihood and the community in the Philippines. According to Abaya *et al.*, (2016), fire occurrences have been steadily increasing, with 12,301 incidents in 2013 rising to 15,897 in 2014, resulting in significant loss of life and property damage. To address this, the Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP) implements safety measures and fire prevention strategies, along with technological advancements that provide further assistance to the BFP and help in preventing fires. However, developing nations like the Philippines face challenges in fire prevention due to limited resources and weak enforcement of regulations. Integrating fire prevention strategies with environmental governance and disaster resilience planning is crucial for minimizing the economic and ecological impact of fire incidents.

Ardani and Permana (2019) discuss how the fire department not only plays the role of combatting fire-related incidents and mishaps but also plays a pivotal role in ensuring community safety, functioning not only as responders to emergencies but also as a department that promotes and establishes fire prevention programs. Fire departments often work collaboratively with local authorities and the public to create fire-safe homes and communities and enhance preparedness against fires and other hazards. They further indicate that these programs increase the community residents' willingness to allow firefighters into their homes for fire-safety inspections, thereby potentially reducing the incidence of residential fires. This collaborative approach emphasizes the importance of understanding fire-related risks and minimizing threats to lives and property. By adopting a community-involved approach, fire departments can effectively promote both fire safety and broader life safety goals through partnerships with community members. As firefighters begin to evolve and develop their understanding of their impact on their community, they must maintain a focus on fostering positive relationships with residents. The approach by the fire department provides not only immediate emergency response but also long-term community resilience.

The role of fire departments in a modern setting has slowly extended beyond just firefighting, according to Bowyer *et al.*, (2016). They have grown to be integral to promoting community safety, emergency response, and public health. Fire departments now operate as both emergency responders and community educators, often taking part in different programs and activities such as fire prevention campaigns and safety training. In some rural environments, volunteer firefighters play a crucial role in sustaining local communities. The role of the fire department in community involvement faces several challenges, especially in rural areas where volunteer work is critical. According to Haynes *et al.*, (2020), one significant issue is the decline in volunteer firefighter membership, which has been attributed to various factors such as time commitment and work-life balance. As communities grow and demands on firefighters increase, potential volunteers may find it difficult to dedicate the necessary time for training and active service. This challenge not only impacts operational capacity but also affects community trust and safety.

In addition to addressing immediate threats, Dampilag (2019) further highlights that the BFP's efforts in fire prevention are vital for mitigating risks associated with urbanization and climate change. Their study on the BFP's capabilities in Marinduque found that while firefighting performance was rated as "Very Satisfactory," there remain substantial gaps in equipment and manpower. This disparity underscores the necessity for improved resource allocation and training programs to bolster the department's efficacy in preventing fires before they escalate into emergencies. Therefore, providing support systems for firefighters is essential not only for their safety but also for maintaining a high level of public trust and allowing them to provide more assistance and support to the community, according to Kurata (2022).

Community development in the Philippine fire service involves various approaches and challenges. Quimbo *et al.*, (2018) indicate that there are growing trends related to the BFP's approach concerning community-

based and participatory methods in development work, with community education and organizing as key strategies. These activities serve to educate and teach the community on the dangers of fire, the importance of fire inspections, and what to do in case fires break out. Community empowerment through volunteer firefighter programs is seen as crucial for improving response times and creating self-reliance. Primo and Collado (2024) further discuss this matter, in that the BFP's fire prevention programs are essential in educating communities about fire safety measures and reducing the incidence of fire-related disasters. Their study presents that the implementation of these programs revealed that while they were generally well-executed, minor issues persisted, highlighting the need for stricter monitoring to ensure compliance with safety policies. However, the challenges faced by BFP personnel significantly impact their ability to foster community engagement effectively. Flora (2025) indicates that firefighters encounter numerous obstacles, including resource scarcity and the physically demanding nature of their work. These challenges create the need to have a collaborative approach that involves local governments and communities to enhance support systems for fire personnel. By investing in resources and fostering cooperation among stakeholders, the BFP can strengthen its community development efforts and improve overall public safety. These highlight the importance of community involvement, resource allocation, and emotional support systems in developing effective fire services and fostering stronger community responses to fire emergencies.

Fire service personnel's competence in fire safety management encompasses a broad range of skills and knowledge, crucial for preventing and managing fires effectively. This includes understanding fire safety regulations, conducting risk assessments, developing fire safety programs, and educating the public on fire safety practices. Echavaria and Espiritu (2024) conducted a comprehensive assessment of fire incidents in Marinduque from 2018 to 2022, evaluating various aspects of firefighting capabilities. This evaluation encompassed fire prevention programs, tools, personal protective equipment (PPE), fire trucks, manpower, skills and training, facilities, infrastructure, and financial resource management. The study aimed to present the performance level in implementing fire prevention programs and determine the significant relationship between firefighting capabilities and the performance of Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP)-Marinduque personnel.

Complementing this, Mendoza (2023) investigated the competence of BFP personnel at the Baguio City Fire Station, with a focus on client satisfaction regarding BFP personnel management. Employing a descriptive quantitative research design, the study assessed the competence of BFP personnel based on responses from 2,963 civilians who had visited the Baguio City Fire Station. Data were gathered using a survey questionnaire and analyzed to reveal that the BFP personnel were competent in cleanliness, orderliness, and promptness and were accommodating towards clients. Overall, respondents described the competence of BFP personnel management as 'excellent.' On a broader scale, Salim *et al.*, (2021) addressed frequent fire incidents in hospitals worldwide, which have devastated humans and resources, causing significant concern among healthcare stakeholders due to the yearly increase in fire outbreaks. While fire safety management has successfully mitigated fires in healthcare facilities, its effectiveness in Malaysian public healthcare facilities has not been extensively studied. This research investigated fire safety management issues in Malaysian public hospitals and suggested possible solutions to improve safety from the operators' perspectives. Objectives were achieved through case studies of five selected public hospitals in Malaysia and a qualitative approach using thematic analysis with MAXQDA software. The findings revealed issues such as lax safety policy implementation, inadequate water pressure, poor maintenance, and insufficient communication systems. The study proposed five main measures to improve fire safety management in public healthcare buildings, including a feasible institutional framework, enhanced emergency response teams, and improved occupational health and safety systems.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for this study is based on the Service Quality (SERVQUAL) Model, developed by Parasuraman *et al.*, (1998). This is also complemented with the theories of Expectancy-Disconfirmation Theory by Oliver (1980) and the Theory of Planned Behavior by Azjen (1991). The main theory anchored in this study, SERVQUAL model, is widely used to assess service quality by measuring the gap between customer expectations and their perceptions of the actual service received. The model focuses on five key dimensions: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy.

This study applied the SERVQUAL model to evaluate community satisfaction with the BFP's frontline services. The tangibles dimension assessed the physical facilities, equipment, and personal appearance. Reliability measured the ability of the BFP to perform the promised service dependably and accurately. Responsiveness evaluated the willingness of the BFP to help and provide prompt service. Assurance

assessed the knowledge and courtesy of BFP personnel and their ability to convey trust and confidence. Lastly, empathy measures the caring and individualized attention the BFP provides to the community. By using the SERVQUAL model, this study systematically examined the perceived effectiveness of the BFP's programs and services in General Mariano Alvarez, Cavite. The model's comprehensive approach helped identify specific areas of strength and areas needing improvement, providing a clear framework for analyzing community satisfaction.

Figure 1. Theoretical framework.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 2. Conceptual framework.

Above is the conceptual framework that guides the data collection and analysis and helps formulate targeted recommendations for improving BFP services based on the community's feedback.

The input represents the variables in this study, which included the respondents' satisfaction levels with the implementation of BFP programs in various aspects. These aspects include fire safety enforcement, firefighting operations, emergency medical services, disaster management, the acceptance and denial of fire safety certificate applications, the issuance of fire safety certificates, a public assistance desk, and a business one-stop shop.

The process outlined how these inputs are transformed into meaningful findings. It includes the methodology for data collection, such as survey design, sampling strategy, and the statistical techniques used to analyze the data. This section ensures that the study is conducted with rigor and transparency. Statistical treatment involves calculating reliability coefficients, performing descriptive statistics to summarize satisfaction levels using its median value, and performing the Kruskal-Wallis test to show significant differences among the variables.

Lastly, the output represents the key outcome of the study, and it reflects how well the BFP's programs are meeting the needs and expectations of the community. In this phase, results from the process phase will provide a detailed picture of how the community views the effectiveness of fire safety enforcement, firefighting operations, emergency medical services, and disaster management.

Significance of the Study

The following will benefit from the findings of the study:

Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP): This study will provide the BFP with valuable insights into how the community perceives its frontline services. The findings will help identify strengths and areas for improvement, enabling the BFP to enhance service quality and effectiveness. By addressing the community's concerns and expectations, the BFP can develop targeted strategies to improve public safety and emergency response in General Mariano Alvarez, Cavite.

Local Government Units (LGUs): The study's results will offer critical information on the effectiveness of fire protection services in local government units' jurisdictions. This knowledge can guide policy-making, resource allocation, and collaboration efforts between the LGUs and the BFP. By understanding the community's satisfaction levels, LGUs can support initiatives that improve fire safety and emergency services, ultimately contributing to the well-being of their constituents.

Community Members: Community members are the primary beneficiaries of improved fire protection services. This study gives them a voice in evaluating the BFP's performance, ensuring their feedback is heard and addressed. The resulting improvements in service quality will directly enhance their safety and quality of life. Additionally, increased awareness of the community's role in fire prevention and safety can foster greater cooperation between the BFP and the public.

Policy Makers: The study will benefit policymakers by helping them understand the current state of fire protection services and community satisfaction. The findings can inform the development of policies and regulations aimed at enhancing the BFP's effectiveness. By considering the community's feedback, policymakers can create more responsive and impactful fire safety regulations that address the specific needs of General Mariano Alvarez, Cavite.

Future Researchers: It will serve as their future reference when they want to broaden the scope of their study. It can also provide additional knowledge about the services and programs offered by the government.

Objectives of the Problem

The objectives of this study is to evaluate the satisfaction levels regarding the implementation of BFP program and the level of implementation of BFP services.

To do this, the following are the aim of the study:

1. To determine the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age
 - 1.2. Gender

- 1.3. Civil status
 - 1.4. Work experience
 - 1.5. Highest educational attainment
2. To investigate the satisfaction level of the respondents in the implementation of the BFP programs in terms of:
 - 2.1. Fire safety enforcement
 - 2.2. Firefighting operations
 - 2.3. Emergency medical services
 - 2.4. Disaster management
 3. To compare the satisfaction levels regarding the implementation of BFP programs when respondents are grouped based on their demographic profiles?
 4. To investigate the satisfaction level of the respondents in the implementation of the BFP services in terms of:
 - 4.1. Acceptance and denial of applications of fire safety certificates
 - 4.2. Issuance of fire safety certificates
 - 4.3. Public assistance desk
 - 4.4. Business one-stop shop (BOSS)
 5. To compare satisfaction levels regarding the implementation of BFP services when respondents are grouped based on their demographic profiles?
 6. Based on the results, to develop an action plan that may be proposed to enhance the program and service implementation at the BFP.

Methodology

This chapter presents the research method, design, population and locale of the study, scope and limitation, data gathering tools, data gathering procedure, treatment of data, ethical considerations and dissemination of findings.

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-evaluative research design to evaluate community satisfaction with the Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP) services in General Mariano Alvarez, Cavite. Quantitative research design is a form of research that investigates research questions using numerical data and statistical analysis. Key components of quantitative research include formulating clear research questions and hypotheses, conducting literature reviews, selecting appropriate methodologies, and developing data collection instruments. Quantitative research is ideal for this study, as it provides a detailed depiction of the current state of BFP services and community perceptions. This design describes the characteristics of a population or phenomenon being studied without influencing it. Using descriptive methods, the study aimed to provide a comprehensive overview of community satisfaction levels and identify specific areas of BFP service that may require improvement.

Further, the quantitative research method is instrumental in understanding the "what" aspect of the research question, providing clear insights into community opinions and experiences with BFP services. It involved collecting data through surveys and questionnaires, enabling the researcher to gather quantitative information on community satisfaction. The data obtained helped analyze the effectiveness of BFP programs in fire safety enforcement, firefighting operations, emergency medical services, and disaster management. This approach ensured that the study captured various community perspectives, leading to a thorough understanding of the BFP's service quality.

Research Method

The research method involved a quantitative approach, utilizing both online and printed questionnaires to gather data from respondents. This method ensures comprehensive data collection, accommodating respondents who prefer digital formats and those who may not have access to the internet. The survey collected quantitative data on various aspects of BFP services, aligning with the study's objectives and research questions. Using structured questionnaires allowed for consistent data collection and facilitated the analysis of community satisfaction levels. The survey included questions related to the demographic profile

of respondents, their satisfaction with BFP services and programs, and their perceptions of the effectiveness of fire safety enforcement, firefighting operations, emergency medical services, and disaster management. Both Likert scale questions captured detailed feedback and numerical data. The research method ensured that data collection was systematic and reliable, providing a robust foundation for analyzing the effectiveness of BFP programs and identifying areas for improvement. This method also allows for efficient data collection from a large sample size, enhancing the study's validity and generalizability.

Population of the Study

This study's population comprises residents of selected barangays and BFP personnel in General Mariano Alvarez, Cavite. The target population includes individuals from various demographic backgrounds, ensuring a representative sample that reflects the diverse community. This includes residents and personnel of different ages, genders, civil statuses, work experiences, and educational attainments. By including a broad cross-section of the community, the study aims to capture various perspectives on the effectiveness of BFP services.

Data Gathering Tools

The primary data-gathering tool for this study was a survey questionnaire designed to capture detailed information on community satisfaction with BFP services. The questionnaire was distributed in digital formats via Google Forms and printed copies to ensure broad accessibility. This dual approach allows for including respondents who prefer online participation and those who may not have internet access, providing comprehensive data collection. The survey contained several sections aligned with the study's objectives and research questions. The first section gathered demographic information about the respondents, including age, gender, civil status, work experience, and educational attainment. The subsequent sections evaluated community satisfaction with various aspects of BFP services, such as fire safety enforcement, firefighting operations, emergency medical services, and disaster management. Questions were formatted using a Likert scale to quantify satisfaction levels, ensuring response consistency.

The development of the questionnaire involved a thorough review of existing literature and consultation with experts in fire protection services to ensure relevance and comprehensiveness. Pre-testing the survey with a small sample of respondents was conducted to refine the questions and improve clarity. This iterative process ensured that the final questionnaire effectively captured the necessary data to evaluate the effectiveness of BFP services from the community's perspective.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data-gathering procedure commenced with preparing and distributing the survey questionnaire. Initially, the questionnaire was designed and pretested with a small sample to ensure its reliability. After revisions based on pretest feedback, the final questionnaire was distributed to respondents in digital and printed formats. The digital version was shared via email and social media platforms using Google Forms, while printed copies were distributed through community centers and local government offices in the selected barangays. Data collection was conducted over a specified period, ensuring ample time for respondents to complete the survey. Both digital and printed responses were collected and compiled for analysis. After data collection, the responses were reviewed for completeness and accuracy. Data from printed questionnaires was manually entered into a digital database to ensure consistency with the online responses. This process was carefully monitored to minimize errors and ensure data integrity. Once all responses were compiled, the data was coded and prepared for analysis using statistical software.

Treatment of Data

Data treatment involved several steps, starting with data cleaning and preparation. Initially, responses were reviewed for completeness, and any incomplete or inconsistent data will be addressed. Data from printed questionnaires was entered into a digital format to create a unified dataset. The dataset was then coded, categorizing responses into meaningful variables that align with the research questions and objectives. Quantitative data from the Likert scale questions were analyzed using descriptive statistics, including measures of central tendency (median) and dispersion (standard deviation). This analysis provided an overview of community satisfaction levels across different aspects of BFP services. Inferential statistics, such as the Kruskal-Wallis test, were used to determine if there are significant differences in satisfaction levels based on demographic variables.

The statistical software used for data analysis included tools like SPSS, suitable for handling large datasets and performing complex statistical analyses. The analysis results were presented in tables and charts to

facilitate easy interpretation and comparison of findings. This systematic approach to data treatment ensured that the study's findings are robust, reliable, and actionable. The final step in data treatment involved synthesizing the results to draw meaningful conclusions and make recommendations. This included interpreting the statistical findings in the context of the study's objectives and existing literature. The insights gained from this analysis informed strategies to enhance the effectiveness of BFP services in General Mariano Alvarez, Cavite, addressing specific areas of concern highlighted by the community.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations are paramount in this study to ensure the integrity and respect for participants. All respondents were informed about the purpose of the study, the voluntary nature of their participation, and their right to withdraw at any time without penalty. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring they understood the nature and objectives of the research. Confidentiality and anonymity of respondents were maintained, with no identifying information being collected or disclosed. The study adhered to ethical guidelines for research involving human participants, ensuring that data were collected, stored, and analyzed responsibly. Any potential risks or discomforts to participants were minimized, and steps were taken to ensure their safety and well-being throughout the research process. The ethical considerations were reviewed and approved by an appropriate ethics review board before the commencement of data collection.

Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results and discussion as well as the analysis and interpretation of the data gathered.

Table 1. Demographic profile of respondents.

Demographic characteristics	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
A. Age		
18-24 years old	56	17.5
25-34 years old	80	25.0
35-44 years old	63	19.7
45-54 years old	60	18.8
55 years old and above	61	19.1
B. Gender		
Male	132	41.3
Female	128	40.0
Others	60	18.8
C. Civil status		
Single	107	33.4
Married	91	28.4
Widowed	84	26.3
Separated	38	11.9
D. Work experience		
Less than 1 year	71	22.2
1-5 years	92	28.8
6-10 years	92	28.8
More than 10 years	65	20.3
E. Highest educational attainment		
Elementary	70	21.9
High school	86	26.9
College	111	34.7
Postgraduate	53	16.6
Total	320	100.0

Table 1 presents the demographic characteristics of the 320 respondents who participated in the study. This demographic profile is essential in understanding the background of the participants and how their personal and professional characteristics might influence their perspectives, behaviors, or responses within the context of the research. The age distribution shows a relatively even spread among the different age brackets. The largest age group is composed of respondents aged 25–34 years, accounting for 25.0% (80 individuals) of the total sample. This is followed by respondents aged 35–44 years (19.7%), 55 years and

above (19.1%), and 45–54 years old (18.8%). The youngest group, 18–24 years old, represents 17.5% of the total. The data suggest that the respondents include a mix of young adults, middle-aged, and older individuals, which can provide a broad range of insights and experiences. The diversity in age may also indicate varying levels of maturity, professional exposure, and engagement in community or institutional affairs.

The gender distribution reveals a relatively balanced representation between males (41.3%) and females (40.0%). Interestingly, a notable percentage of respondents identified as “Others” (18.8%), which may include individuals from the LGBTQ+ community or those who do not conform to traditional gender classifications. The inclusion of diverse gender identities suggests that the study was conducted with sensitivity to gender inclusivity, allowing for more comprehensive and equitable data collection. In terms of civil status, the largest group is single respondents (33.4%), followed by married individuals (28.4%), widowed (26.3%), and separated (11.9%). This distribution highlights that while a significant number of respondents are unmarried, a considerable proportion are either married or have experienced changes in marital status. Civil status can influence responsibilities, stress levels, and decision-making, especially in studies related to employment, community involvement, or public service roles.

The respondents show a varied range of work experience. Those with 1–5 years (28.8%) and 6–10 years (28.8%) form the largest groups, suggesting that most participants have moderate experience in their respective fields. Those with less than 1 year (22.2%) may be new entrants to the workforce, while 20.3% of respondents have more than 10 years of experience, indicating a seasoned group that can provide insights based on long-term involvement. The diversity in work experience may help identify whether perceptions or competencies vary depending on the length of professional service. Regarding educational background, a majority of respondents have attained college-level education (34.7%), followed by high school graduates (26.9%) and elementary-level education (21.9%). A significant portion, 16.6%, have completed postgraduate studies. This educational profile implies that many respondents are relatively well-educated, which may influence their understanding, communication skills, and participation in community or organizational processes. Those with lower levels of education may still provide valuable insights, particularly if the study involves grassroots-level issues or public service delivery. In conclusion, the demographic data presented in Table 1 illustrates that the study’s respondents come from diverse backgrounds in terms of age, gender identity, civil status, work experience, and educational attainment.

Table 2. Level of satisfaction in the implementation of the BFP programs in terms of fire safety enforcement.

Indicators	Resident		BFP	
	Med	Int	Med	Int
1. The BFP conducts regular fire safety inspections in my community.	3.54	VS	3.60	VS
2. The BFP ensures compliance with fire safety regulations.	3.58	VS	3.55	VS
3. The BFP provides adequate information on fire safety measures.	3.54	VS	3.70	VS
4. The BFP's fire safety programs are effective.	3.52	VS	3.80	VS
5. The BFP promptly addresses fire safety violations.	3.35	VS	3.45	VS
6. The BFP educates the community about fire prevention.	3.52	VS	3.55	VS
7. The BFP's fire safety guidelines are clear and understandable.	3.54	VS	3.75	VS
8. The BFP's inspections help in reducing fire risks.	3.48	VS	3.35	VS
9. The BFP collaborates with local authorities on fire safety.	3.53	VS	3.60	VS
10. The BFP provides timely updates on fire safety regulations.	3.51	VS	3.50	VS
Overall	3.52	VS	3.68	VS
*Legend: VS: Very satisfied, S: Satisfied, D: Dissatisfied, VD: Very dissatisfied				

Table 2 presents the level of satisfaction with the implementation of the BFP programs in terms of fire safety enforcement as perceived by residents in the area and BFP personnel. The values of 3.52 for residents and 3.68 for BFP personnel indicate that overall, both residents and BFP personnel are very satisfied with the programs implemented by the BFP in terms of fire safety enforcement. These results show a very satisfactory rating on both BFP personnel and residents, showing how regular fire safety inspections play a crucial role in reducing fire risks and ensuring occupant safety. These inspections involve evaluating fire prevention measures, detection systems, evacuation plans, and emergency response procedures. By identifying potential hazards, equipment deficiencies, and areas not meeting safety regulations, regular inspections contribute to creating a safer environment and reducing the likelihood of fire-related incidents. The high satisfaction levels reported by BFP personnel regarding the effectiveness of their fire safety

programs highlight the organization’s internal commitment to safety protocols and continuous improvement. This confidence within the BFP may lead to more effective enforcement and community educational initiatives, directly benefiting residents.

Table 3. Level of satisfaction in the implementation of the BFP programs in terms of firefighting operations.

Indicators	Resident		BFP	
	Med	Int	Med	Int
1. The BFP responds promptly to fire incidents in my area.	3.50	VS	3.45	VS
2. The BFP effectively controls and extinguishes fires.	3.56	VS	3.65	VS
3. The BFP has adequate firefighting equipment.	3.58	VS	3.70	VS
4. The BFP personnel are well-trained for firefighting.	3.50	VS	3.55	VS
5. The BFP's firefighting strategies are effective.	3.55	VS	3.65	VS
6. The BFP maintains a visible presence in the community.	3.57	VS	3.50	VS
7. The BFP collaborates with other emergency services during fires.	3.48	VS	3.30	VS
8. The BFP keeps the community informed during fire incidents.	3.54	VS	3.55	VS
9. The BFP conducts regular firefighting drills.	3.52	VS	3.40	VS
10. The BFP effectively mitigates damage during fires.	3.53	VS	3.30	VS
Overall	3.54	VS	3.46	VS

*Legend: VS: Very satisfied, S: Satisfied, D: Dissatisfied, VD: Very dissatisfied

The overall level of satisfaction in the implementation of the Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP) programs in terms of firefighting operations is rated as Very Satisfied (VS) by both residents (3.54) and BFP personnel (3.46). This indicates a generally positive perception of the BFP’s firefighting efforts from both groups. These results indicate that while the BFP is generally effective, there may be challenges in inter-agency coordination and post-fire damage control. The findings suggest a need for improved collaboration with other emergency services and enhanced mitigation strategies to further strengthen firefighting operations. The adequacy of firefighting equipment is crucial for effective emergency response. Studies have shown that reliable and well-maintained equipment enhances firefighters' ability to control and extinguish fires efficiently, thereby reducing potential damage and casualties. This shows that the high satisfaction levels reported by both residents and BFP personnel can be attributed to the adequacy of firefighting equipment, the agency's visible community presence, and the effectiveness of their firefighting strategies. These factors not only enhance the efficiency of firefighting operations but also strengthen the relationship between the BFP and the communities they serve.

Table 4. Level of satisfaction in the implementation of the BFP programs in terms of emergency medical services.

Indicators	Resident		BFP	
	Med	Int	Med	Int
1. The BFP provides timely emergency medical assistance.	3.50	VS	3.45	VS
2. The BFP personnel are skilled in providing medical assistance.	3.51	VS	3.45	VS
3. The BFP's emergency medical services are reliable.	3.56	VS	3.55	VS
4. The BFP has adequate medical equipment.	3.45	VS	3.50	VS
5. The BFP's emergency medical services are accessible.	3.53	VS	3.65	VS
6. The BFP personnel show empathy and care.	3.49	VS	3.60	VS
7. The BFP collaborates with hospitals and clinics effectively.	3.53	VS	3.45	VS
8. The BFP conducts regular training for emergency medical services.	3.54	VS	3.35	VS
9. The BFP's emergency medical services are well-organized.	3.54	VS	3.70	VS
10. The BFP provides follow-up care after medical emergencies.	3.54	VS	3.65	VS
Overall	3.51	VS	3.39	VS

*Legend: VS: Very satisfied, S: Satisfied, D: Dissatisfied, VD: Very dissatisfied

The overall level of satisfaction with the implementation of the Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP) programs in terms of emergency medical services is rated as Very Satisfied (VS) by both residents (3.51) and BFP personnel (3.39). This suggests that while both groups view the emergency medical services positively, BFP personnel have a slightly lower level of satisfaction compared to residents. The satisfaction levels regarding the BFP's EMS can be attributed to several factors, including the ongoing training and certification of personnel as emergency medical technicians (EMTs). Recent legislative efforts, such as House Bill 6512, mandate that BFP personnel receive adequate training to enhance their emergency response capabilities.

This requirement is crucial, as it ensures that responders are equipped with the essential skills necessary for effective pre-hospital care, which can significantly impact patient outcomes during emergencies. Furthermore, the emphasis on collaboration with hospitals and clinics enhances the overall efficacy of emergency responses, allowing for a seamless transition from on-site care to hospital treatment. These findings highlight the importance of ongoing training and community engagement in enhancing the effectiveness of emergency medical services provided by the BFP.

Table 5. Level of satisfaction in the implementation of the BFP programs in terms of disaster management.

Indicators	Resident		BFP	
	Med	Int	Med	Int
1. The BFP is well-prepared to handle disasters.	3.55	VS	3.65	VS
2. The BFP conducts regular disaster preparedness drills.	3.51	VS	3.35	VS
3. The BFP effectively communicates disaster management plans to the community.	3.60	VS	3.55	VS
4. The BFP collaborates with other agencies for disaster management.	3.53	VS	3.55	VS
5. The BFP's disaster management strategies are effective.	3.50	VS	3.70	VS
6. The BFP has adequate resources for disaster response.	3.54	VS	3.65	VS
7. The BFP provides timely updates during disasters.	3.55	VS	3.65	VS
8. The BFP helps the community recover after disasters.	3.46	VS	3.85	VS
9. The BFP personnel are trained for disaster management.	3.52	VS	3.55	VS
10. The BFP's disaster management efforts have improved over time.	3.51	VS	3.65	VS
Overall	3.51	VS	3.73	VS

*Legend: VS: Very satisfied, S: Satisfied, D: Dissatisfied, VD: Very dissatisfied

The results in Table 5 indicate a very satisfactory level of satisfaction among both residents and Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP) personnel regarding the implementation of BFP programs in disaster management. The overall satisfaction rating of residents (3.51) is slightly lower than that of BFP personnel (3.73), suggesting that while both groups perceive the BFP's disaster management efforts positively, BFP personnel have a more favorable assessment of their own preparedness and response capabilities. The findings indicate that both the community and BFP personnel are very satisfied with the implementation of disaster management programs. The BFP is perceived to be well-prepared, coordinated, communicative, and continuously improving. Minor areas for improvement include increasing community involvement in drills and enhancing visible recovery efforts post-disaster. The BFP's collaboration with other agencies and communication of disaster management plans were also rated highly. However, the indicator on conducting regular disaster preparedness drills received one of the lower ratings from both groups. This indicates that while disaster drills are widely recognized as essential, their effectiveness depends on proper and frequent implementation. The need for continuous training and evaluation of these drills is emphasized in disaster risk reduction frameworks.

Table 6. Comparative analysis in the level of satisfaction in the implementation of the BFP programs among the age of respondents.

BFP programs	Age										Kruskal-Wallis H-value	Test statistics p-value
	18-24		25-34		35-44		45-54		55 and above			
	Md	Int	Md	Int	Md	Int	Md	Int	Md	Int		
Fire safety enforcement	3.46	VS	3.57	VS	3.61	VS	3.51	VS	3.47	VS	2.515	0.642
Firefighting operations	3.58	VS	3.59	VS	3.51	VS	3.53	VS	3.49	VS	1.142	0.887
Emergency medical services	3.64	VS	3.47	VS	3.52	VS	3.49	VS	3.45	VS	2.818	0.589
Disaster management	3.46	VS	3.63	VS	3.53	VS	3.56	VS	3.43	VS	4.293	0.368

*Significant @ ≤ 0.05 ; Legend: VS: Very satisfied, S: Satisfied, D: Dissatisfied, VD: Very dissatisfied

Table 6 presents the comparative analysis of the level of satisfaction in the implementation of the BFP programs among the age groups of respondents.

In comparing whether the difference is significant, a non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test was applied, wherein a p-value of less than or equal to 0.050 indicates that the difference is significant. The p-values of the BFP programs do not indicate that there is a significant difference between the ages of the respondents. This indicates that all different age groups of respondents have the same level of satisfaction with the implementation of the BFP programs. The uniform satisfaction across different age groups may be attributed to the BFP's standardized and inclusive approach in implementing its programs. Studies have shown that when public safety services maintain consistency in training, response protocols, and community engagement, satisfaction levels tend to remain high across various demographics. This universal positive perception may also be influenced by the increasing public awareness of fire safety and disaster preparedness, which is often reinforced through local government initiatives and community-based programs.

Table 7. Comparative analysis in the level of satisfaction in the implementation of the BFP programs among the gender of respondents.

BFP programs	Gender						Kruskal-Wallis H-value	Test statistics p-value
	Male		Female		Other			
	Med	Int	Med	Int	Med	Int		
Fire safety enforcement	3.54	VS	3.56	VS	3.47	VS	0.600	0.741
Firefighting operations	3.48	VS	3.50	VS	3.72	VS	8.467	0.015*
Emergency medical services	3.55	VS	3.49	VS	3.46	VS	0.758	0.685
Disaster management	3.45	VS	3.57	VS	3.61	VS	3.442	0.179
*Significant @ ≤ 0.05 ; Legend: VS: Very satisfied, S: Satisfied, D: Dissatisfied, VD: Very dissatisfied								

In comparing whether the difference is significant between the gender of the respondents, a non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test was applied. When looking at the results, it indicates that firefighting operations, with an H-value of 8.467 and a corresponding p-value of 0.015, are significant.

The overall very satisfactory ratings highlight the importance of equitable service delivery in emergency response and disaster management. When fire protection agencies maintain consistency in training, communication, and community engagement, public satisfaction remains high regardless of gender. Additionally, the accessibility and responsiveness of emergency services contribute significantly to trust and satisfaction levels across diverse populations.

However, the results of the Kruskal-Wallis test reveal a statistically significant difference in satisfaction levels regarding firefighting operations among gender groups, with a p-value of 0.015. This suggests that gender influences perceptions of firefighting performance, with respondents identifying as "Other" reporting the highest satisfaction (3.72) compared to male (3.48) and female (3.50) respondents.

The observed difference in satisfaction levels may be attributed to various factors. Men and women may have different expectations of emergency response effectiveness, with women placing more emphasis on community-based disaster preparedness, while men may prioritize operational efficiency. Additionally, individuals identifying outside the traditional binary gender categories may have unique perspectives on inclusivity and responsiveness in emergency services, potentially leading to higher satisfaction ratings when agencies demonstrate gender-sensitive approaches.

Table 8. Post-hoc analysis in the level of satisfaction in the implementation of the BFP programs among the gender of respondents along firefighting operations.

Grp	Med	Grp	Med	Sig.
Male	3.48	Female	3.50	0.751
		Other	3.72	0.005*
Female	3.50	Other	3.72	0.012*
*Significant @ ≤ 0.05				

Table 8 presents the post-hoc analysis of the level of satisfaction in the implementation of the BFP programs among the gender respondents along with firefighting operations. Comparing the level of satisfaction of males (3.48) with others (3.72), the p-value of 0.005 indicates that the difference is significant. The same was observed in comparing females (3.50) with the others (3.72), with a p-value of 0.012. These results indicate that those identifying as "Other" report a significantly higher level of satisfaction with firefighting operations compared to their male and female counterparts.

One possible explanation for this finding is that individuals outside the traditional gender binary may place a higher value on inclusivity and equitable treatment in public services. When agencies like the Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP) implement inclusive policies, these individuals may feel more acknowledged, leading to increased satisfaction. A study on gender differences in firefighter job stressors and symptoms of stress found that female firefighters reported significantly higher scores on job skill concerns, indicating that inclusivity efforts can enhance satisfaction among marginalized groups.

Another factor could be the perception of accessibility and responsiveness in firefighting operations. Gender-diverse individuals often have heightened awareness of safety and emergency preparedness due to societal vulnerabilities. If firefighting operations demonstrate strong community engagement and effective response mechanisms, these individuals may recognize and appreciate these efforts more distinctly, resulting in higher satisfaction. Research indicates that female firefighters face unique challenges in a male-dominated field, and efforts to address these can improve job satisfaction. Additionally, marginalized groups may evaluate emergency services based on factors such as sensitivity to community needs and communication efforts. If the BFP has engaged in targeted outreach and awareness programs, individuals identifying as "Other" may feel a greater sense of trust and confidence in their services.

Table 9. Comparative analysis of the level of satisfaction in the implementation of the BFP programs among the civil status of respondents.

BFP programs	Civil status								Kruskal-Wallis H-value	Test statistics p-value
	Single		Married		Widowed		Separated			
	Md	Int	Md	Int	Md	Int	Md	Int		
Fire safety enforcement	3.49	VS	3.57	VS	3.54	VS	3.56	VS	0.679	0.878
Firefighting operations	3.55	VS	3.47	VS	3.60	VS	3.54	VS	1.596	0.661
Emergency medical services	3.44	VS	3.53	VS	3.57	VS	3.54	VS	2.131	0.546
Disaster management	3.48	VS	3.58	VS	3.51	VS	3.60	VS	1.530	0.675

*Significant @ ≤ 0.05 ; Legend: VS: Very satisfied, S: Satisfied, D: Dissatisfied, VD: Very dissatisfied

Table 9 presents a comparative analysis of the level of satisfaction with the implementation of BFP programs among respondents with different civil status categories. The consistent "Very Satisfied" ratings across all civil status groups suggest that the BFP's programs are well-received by the community, regardless of differences in marital status.

The application of the Kruskal-Wallis test shows that none of the p-values are significant ($p > 0.05$), indicating that there is no statistically significant difference in satisfaction levels among the different civil status groups. This suggests that the perception of BFP services is uniform across various demographic categories, reflecting the agency's equitable approach in providing emergency services. Research suggests that public satisfaction with emergency response services is generally influenced by accessibility, efficiency, and effectiveness rather than demographic factors such as civil status.

One reason for the consistent satisfaction levels could be that fire protection and emergency response services are community-wide initiatives that benefit all individuals regardless of their civil status. The lack of significant differences suggests that these services are equally accessible and effective for all individuals, whether single, married, widowed, or separated.

Table 10. Comparative analysis of the level of satisfaction in the implementation of the BFP programs among the work experience of respondents.

BFP programs	Work experience								Kruskal-Wallis H-value	Test statistics p-value
	Less than 1 year		1-5 years		6-10 years		More than 10 years			
	Md	Int	Md	Int	Md	Int	Md	Int		
Fire safety enforcement	3.53	VS	3.55	VS	3.54	VS	3.50	VS	0.233	0.972
Firefighting operations	3.57	VS	3.42	VS	3.62	VS	3.55	VS	4.943	0.176
Emergency medical services	3.54	VS	3.62	VS	3.47	VS	3.70	VS	6.312	0.097
Disaster management	3.58	VS	3.51	VS	3.50	VS	3.55	VS	0.676	0.876

*Significant @ ≤ 0.05 ; Legend: VS: Very satisfied, S: Satisfied, D: Dissatisfied, VD: Very dissatisfied

Table 10 presents the comparative analysis of the level of satisfaction in the implementation of BFP programs among respondents with varying levels of work experience. The results show that all groups—those with less than one year, 1–5 years, 6–10 years, and more than 10 years of work experience—expressed a “Very Satisfied” rating across all BFP programs, including fire safety enforcement, firefighting operations, emergency medical services, and disaster management. The uniform satisfaction levels indicate that the BFP programs are perceived positively across different experience levels, suggesting that the agency has maintained consistent service quality and effectiveness regardless of the respondents' professional tenure.

The application of the Kruskal-Wallis test further supports these findings, as none of the p-values are below the 0.05 threshold, indicating no statistically significant differences in satisfaction levels across different work experience groups. This suggests that perceptions of BFP programs are independent of professional tenure. This entails that satisfaction with public safety services is more strongly influenced by service reliability and accessibility rather than by an individual's length of experience in a profession. One possible reason for the uniform satisfaction levels is the structured and standardized approach of the BFP in implementing its programs. Emergency response and fire protection agencies that adhere to strict protocols and systematic training often achieve high and consistent satisfaction ratings among the public. The BFP's adherence to fire safety regulations, emergency response training, and disaster management protocols likely ensures that individuals across different professional experience levels perceive their services as effective.

Table 11. Comparative analysis in the level of satisfaction in the implementation of the BFP programs among the highest educational attainment of respondents.

BFP programs	Highest educational attainment								Kruskal-Wallis H-value	Test statistics p-value
	Elementary		High school		College		Postgraduate			
	Md	Int	Md	Int	Md	Int	Md	Int		
Fire safety enforcement	3.41	VS	3.54	VS	3.55	VS	3.63	VS	3.535	0.316
Firefighting operations	3.49	VS	3.58	VS	3.51	VS	3.59	VS	1.224	0.747
Emergency medical services	3.55	VS	3.48	VS	3.49	VS	3.55	VS	0.528	0.913
Disaster management	3.54	VS	3.52	VS	3.49	VS	3.61	VS	1.332	0.722

*Significant @ ≤ 0.05 ; Legend: VS: Very satisfied, S: Satisfied, D: Dissatisfied, VD: Very dissatisfied

Table 11 presents the comparative analysis of the level of satisfaction in the implementation of BFP programs among respondents with different levels of educational attainment. The findings reveal that all educational groups—elementary, high school, college, and postgraduate—reported a “Very Satisfied” (VS)

rating across all BFP programs. The Kruskal-Wallis H-value and corresponding p-values provide further context to these satisfaction levels. For instance, the H-value for fire safety enforcement was 3.535 with a p-value of 0.316, indicating no statistically significant difference in satisfaction based on educational attainment at the 0.05 level. Similar results were observed for the other programs, with H-values ranging from 1.224 to 1.332 and p-values between 0.722 and 0.913, all of which exceed the significance threshold ($p \leq 0.05$). This lack of statistical significance suggests that educational attainment does not influence satisfaction levels regarding BFP programs.

The findings emphasize the importance of community awareness and satisfaction in fire safety services. Public awareness significantly correlates with satisfaction levels in fire service delivery, emphasizing that effective communication and community engagement are crucial for enhancing public trust and satisfaction. Moreover, community engagement initiatives by fire departments lead to improved perceptions of service effectiveness, regardless of the respondents' educational backgrounds.

Table 12. Level of satisfaction in the implementation of the BFP services in terms of acceptance and denial of applications of fire safety certificates.

Indicators	Resident		BFP	
	Med	Int	Med	Int
1. The criteria for accepting or denying applications for fire safety certificates are clear.	3.60	VS	3.60	VS
2. The communication regarding the acceptance or denial of my application is timely.	3.50	VS	3.89	VS
3. The explanation provided when an application is denied is satisfactory.	3.50	VS	3.50	VS
4. The staff handling the applications for fire safety certificates are approachable and ready to answer questions.	3.54	VS	3.90	VS
5. The process for reapplying or appealing a denied fire safety certificate is straightforward and transparent.	3.55	VS	3.55	VS
Overall	3.55	VS	3.85	VS

*Legend: VS: Very satisfied, S: Satisfied, D: Dissatisfied, VD: Very dissatisfied

The values of 3.55 for residents and 3.85 for BFP personnel indicate that overall, both residents and BFP personnel are very satisfied with the services implemented by the BFP in terms of acceptance and denial of applications for fire safety certificates.

These findings align with previous research emphasizing the importance of clear communication and efficient processes in public service satisfaction. For instance, a study by Qualtrics and Civic Pulse found that 75% of recent hires were satisfied with the government hiring process, underscoring the significance of clear criteria and timely communication in public sector satisfaction. In conclusion, the high satisfaction ratings across all indicators suggest that the BFP's processes for handling fire safety certificate applications are effective and well-received by both residents and personnel. Maintaining clear criteria, timely communication, satisfactory explanations for denials, approachable staff, and transparent reapplication procedures are crucial for sustaining this high level of satisfaction.

Table 13. Level of satisfaction in the implementation of the BFP services in terms of issuance of fire safety certificates.

Indicators	Resident		BFP	
	Med	Int	Med	Int
1. The process for issuing fire safety certificates is efficient.	3.52	VS	3.55	VS
2. The staff involved in issuing fire safety certificates are professional.	3.57	VS	3.60	VS
3. The overall time it takes to receive a fire safety certificate is satisfactory.	3.53	VS	3.65	VS
4. The documentation required for the issuance of fire safety certificates is clear and easy to understand.	3.55	VS	3.50	VS
5. The fees associated with the issuance of fire safety certificates are reasonable and transparent.	3.59	VS	3.60	VS
Overall	3.55	VS	3.60	VS

*Legend: VS: Very satisfied, S: Satisfied, D: Dissatisfied, VD: Very dissatisfied

Table 13 presents the median satisfaction ratings from both residents and Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP) personnel regarding the issuance of fire safety certificates. Both groups expressed "Very Satisfied" (VS) ratings across all indicators, with overall median scores of 3.55 for residents and 3.60 for BFP personnel.

Satisfaction with the overall time taken to receive a fire safety certificate suggests that both groups find the processing time acceptable. The reasonableness and transparency of associated fees highlights satisfaction with the financial aspects of the certification process. These findings align with previous research emphasizing the importance of efficiency, professionalism, and transparency in public service delivery. These findings suggest that while the fire safety certificate issuance process is perceived as professional and well-managed, optimizing efficiency and simplifying paperwork could further enhance satisfaction levels.

In conclusion, the high satisfaction ratings across all indicators suggest that the BFP's processes for issuing fire safety certificates are effective and well-received by both residents and personnel. Maintaining efficient procedures, professional staff conduct, reasonable processing times, clear documentation requirements, and transparent fee structures are crucial for sustaining this high level of satisfaction.

Table 14. Level of satisfaction in the implementation of the BFP services in terms of public assistance desk.

Indicators	Resident		BFP	
	Med	Int	Med	Int
1. The public assistance desk is helpful in addressing my concerns.	3.51	VS	3.50	VS
2. The public assistance desk is easily accessible.	3.49	VS	3.50	VS
3. The staff at the public assistance desk are polite and professional.	3.53	VS	3.55	VS
4. The public assistance desk provides accurate information and guidance.	3.57	VS	3.55	VS
5. The staff provides fast response time for inquiries at the public assistance desk.	3.53	VS	3.55	VS
Overall	3.51	VS	3.50	VS

*Legend: VS: Very satisfied, S: Satisfied, D: Dissatisfied, VD: Very dissatisfied

Table 14 presents the median satisfaction ratings from both residents and Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP) personnel regarding the public assistance desk. Both groups expressed "Very Satisfied" ratings across all indicators, with overall median scores of 3.51 for residents and 3.50 for BFP personnel.

These findings highlight how the quality of help desk support significantly influences user satisfaction, particularly in terms of responsiveness and professionalism. Additionally, an increase in public satisfaction with federal government services can be attributed to improvements to better service delivery and communication.

This shows that the high satisfaction ratings across all indicators suggest that the BFP's public assistance desk effectively meets the needs of both residents and personnel. Maintaining helpfulness, accessibility, professionalism, accurate information dissemination, and prompt responses is crucial for sustaining this high level of satisfaction.

Table 15. Level of satisfaction in the implementation of the BFP services in terms of business one-stop shop (BOSS).

Indicators	Resident		BFP	
	Med	Int	Med	Int
1. The business one-stop shop (BOSS) is convenient for handling multiple transactions in one place.	3.50	VS	3.70	VS
2. The BOSS is efficient in processing business-related applications and permits.	3.52	VS	3.65	VS
3. The overall experience at the BOSS is satisfactory.	3.50	VS	3.65	VS
4. The BOSS staff are knowledgeable and efficient in assisting with my transactions.	3.50	VS	3.80	VS
5. The BOSS provides clear guidelines for the requirements and steps needed for each business application process.	3.49	VS	3.45	VS
Overall	3.50	VS	3.80	VS

*Legend: VS: Very satisfied, S: Satisfied, D: Dissatisfied, VD: Very dissatisfied

Table 15 presents the level of satisfaction in the implementation of BFP services at the business one-stop shop (BOSS), as perceived by both residents and BFP personnel. The overall satisfaction levels indicate a high degree of satisfaction, with residents reporting a mean score of 3.50 and BFP personnel reporting a slightly higher mean of 3.80, both indicating "Very Satisfied" ratings.

These results suggest that both residents and BFP personnel view the BOSS as a well-functioning service, with both groups recognizing its convenience, efficiency, and professionalism in handling business-related applications and permits.

These results indicate that the BOSS has been effective in providing convenient, efficient, and professional services to residents and BFP personnel. To further enhance satisfaction, the BFP could consider improving the clarity of guidelines and instructions for business applications. Additionally, expanding digital solutions, such as online application platforms or automated tracking systems, could further streamline processes and make the BOSS even more accessible and user-friendly.

Table 16. Comparative analysis in the level of satisfaction in the implementation of the BFP services among the age of respondents.

BFP services	Age										Kruskal-Wallis H-value	Test statistics p-value
	18-24		25-34		35-44		45-54		55 and above			
	Md	Int	Md	Int	Md	Int	Md	Int	Md	Int		
Acceptance and denial of applications of fire safety certificates	3.54	VS	3.63	VS	3.60	VS	3.57	VS	3.49	VS	3.050	0.550
Issuance of fire safety certificates	3.55	VS	3.56	VS	3.62	VS	3.62	VS	3.41	VS	7.161	0.128
Public assistance desk	3.41	VS	3.54	VS	3.56	VS	3.57	VS	3.46	VS	4.365	0.359
Business one-stop shop (BOSS)	3.50	VS	3.54	VS	3.49	VS	3.50	VS	3.54	VS	0.562	0.967
*Significant @ ≤ 0.05 ; Legend: VS: Very satisfied, S: Satisfied, D: Dissatisfied, VD: Very dissatisfied												

When assessing the level of satisfaction of the BFP services along the age of the respondents, it shows that all age groups are very satisfied with all the programs of the BFP.

In comparing whether the difference is significant, a non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test was applied, wherein a p-value of less than or equal to 0.050 indicates that the difference is significant. The p-values of the BFP services do not indicate that there is a significant difference between the ages of the respondents. This finding can be attributed to several factors. First, the BFP's services, such as the issuance of fire safety certificates and public assistance, are essential for the safety and well-being of all individuals, regardless of age. Research has shown that emergency services and safety programs that benefit the community tend to foster a shared sense of satisfaction. When fire safety agencies provide clear, efficient, and accessible services, people of all ages are likely to appreciate the value of these programs.

Furthermore, the high satisfaction ratings could be indicative of the BFP's effective communication and public engagement efforts, which reach diverse age groups. Well-structured public safety services that involve outreach and information dissemination tend to foster positive perceptions across various demographic segments. Since fire safety concerns affect everyone, the BFP's commitment to clear communication, accessibility, and professional service likely resonates with all respondents, leading to uniformly high satisfaction across age categories.

It is also worth considering that, regardless of age, the BFP's services offer essential benefits that directly impact the safety and security of individuals and communities. Programs like the business one-stop shop (BOSS) streamline processes and reduce bureaucracy, which benefits business owners and residents of all ages. In particular, the BOSS's convenience, efficiency, and centralized service model are likely to be appreciated universally. Centralized services save time and reduce the complexity of navigating multiple administrative processes, which increases satisfaction levels for individuals across age groups.

Additionally, older age groups (55 and above) may have more experience interacting with public service agencies and may have seen improvements in the efficiency and accessibility of services over time. Long-term residents often appreciate the stability and reliability of emergency services, which may contribute to their satisfaction. Conversely, younger respondents (18-24) may value the efficiency and modernization of services, especially those related to technology and accessibility, which can also explain their high level of satisfaction.

Table 17. Comparative analysis in the level of satisfaction in the implementation of the BFP services among the gender of respondents.

BFP services	Gender						Kruskal-Wallis H-value	Test statistics p-value
	Male		Female		Other			
	Med	Int	Med	Int	Med	Int		
Acceptance and denial of applications of fire safety certificates	3.57	VS	3.61	VS	3.48	VS	2.638	0.267
Issuance of fire safety certificates	3.61	VS	3.52	VS	3.50	VS	3.358	0.187
Public assistance desk	3.55	VS	3.48	VS	3.50	VS	1.256	0.534
Business one-stop shop (BOSS)	3.55	VS	3.49	VS	3.50	VS	0.808	0.668

*Significant @ ≤ 0.05 ; Legend: VS: Very satisfied, S: Satisfied, D: Dissatisfied, VD: Very dissatisfied

Table 17 presents a comparative analysis of the level of satisfaction in the implementation of BFP services across different gender groups, including male, female, and other gender identities. The results indicate that all gender groups reported "Very Satisfied" (VS) ratings across all BFP services. The satisfaction levels are uniformly high, with no significant differences between the groups, as indicated by the Kruskal-Wallis test ($p > 0.05$).

The lack of statistically significant differences (with p-values ranging from 0.187 to 0.534) suggests that satisfaction with BFP services is largely independent of gender. This finding is consistent with the idea that fire safety services, as well as public assistance and business support services, are universal and essential for the entire community, regardless of gender. Research indicates that public safety services that are perceived as equitable, efficient, and accessible tend to generate similar levels of satisfaction across various demographic groups. In the case of the BFP, this includes both traditional gender categories (male and female) and individuals identifying as "Other."

Table 18. Comparative analysis in the level of satisfaction in the implementation of the BFP services among the civil status of respondents.

BFP services	Civil status								Kruskal-Wallis H-value	Test statistics p-value
	Single		Married		Widowed		Separated			
	Md	Int	Md	Int	Md	Int	Md	Int		
Acceptance and denial of applications of fire safety certificates	3.55	VS	3.59	VS	3.56	VS	3.58	VS	0.401	0.940
Issuance of fire safety certificates	3.53	VS	3.54	VS	3.62	VS	3.50	VS	2.164	0.539
Public assistance desk	3.52	VS	3.41	VS	3.58	VS	3.55	VS	6.035	0.110
Business one-stop shop (BOSS)	3.56	VS	3.54	VS	3.48	VS	3.42	VS	2.937	0.401

*Significant @ ≤ 0.05 ; Legend: VS: Very satisfied, S: Satisfied, D: Dissatisfied, VD: Very dissatisfied

Table 18 presents a comparative analysis of the level of satisfaction in the implementation of BFP services across different civil status groups, including single, married, widowed, and separated respondents. The results show that all groups reported "Very Satisfied" (VS) ratings for the various BFP services. The satisfaction levels are high across all civil status categories, and no significant differences were found between the groups (with p-values ranging from 0.110 to 0.940), as indicated by the Kruskal-Wallis test.

The absence of significant differences in satisfaction levels suggests that satisfaction with BFP services is largely independent of respondents' civil status. This finding suggests that public services like fire safety and business assistance are universally essential, and individuals from all civil status backgrounds benefit equally from these services. For the Business one-stop shop (BOSS), which is designed to facilitate the handling of multiple business-related transactions in one location, there were no significant differences between civil status groups, either, with scores ranging from 3.42 to 3.58. This suggests that the BOSS is universally appreciated by all civil status categories for its convenience and efficiency. Centralized service models, as exemplified by the BOSS, are recognized for improving customer satisfaction because they streamline processes and reduce bureaucratic delays.

Table 19. Comparative analysis in the level of satisfaction in the implementation of the BFP services among the work experience of respondents.

BFP services	Work experience								Kruskal-Wallis H-value	Test statistics p-value
	Less than 1 year		1-5 years		6-10 years		More than 10 years			
	Md	Int	Md	Int	Md	Int	Md	Int		
Acceptance and denial of applications of fire safety certificates	3.58	VS	3.53	VS	3.55	VS	3.63	VS	1.604	0.658
Issuance of fire safety certificates	3.58	VS	3.54	VS	3.58	VS	3.51	VS	0.941	0.816
Public assistance desk	3.62	VS	3.39	VS	3.48	VS	3.60	VS	11.049	0.011*
Business one-stop shop (BOSS)	3.54	VS	3.48	VS	3.55	VS	3.49	VS	1.313	0.726

*Significant @ ≤ 0.05 ; Legend: VS: Very satisfied, S: Satisfied, D: Dissatisfied, VD: Very dissatisfied

Table 19 presents a comparative analysis of the level of satisfaction in the implementation of the BFP services along with the work experience of the respondents. When assessing the level of satisfaction of the BFP program along with the work experience of the respondents, it shows that all respondents with varying work experiences are very satisfied with all the programs of the BFP. When looking at the results, it indicates that the public assistance desk, with an H-value of 11.049 and a corresponding p-value of 0.011, is significant.

The lack of significant differences in satisfaction across work experience groups for most BFP services suggests that the satisfaction levels are largely consistent regardless of how long respondents have been working. This is consistent with findings in public administration research, where satisfaction with public services often depends more on the perceived quality of service and less on individual work experience. Whether respondents are new employees or long-term professionals, the fundamental need for reliable and efficient emergency services is universal. Thus, satisfaction is driven by the effectiveness, accessibility, and professionalism of the services, rather than the respondents' work experience.

However, the significant difference observed in the public assistance desk, with a p-value of 0.011 (H-value = 11.049), indicates that satisfaction with this service is influenced by the respondents' work experience. Respondents with more than 10 years of work experience had a satisfaction score of 3.60, which was closer to that of the less than 1-year group.

This variation in satisfaction could be attributed to the differing expectations and perceptions of individuals based on their level of work experience. Individuals with less work experience might have higher satisfaction due to fewer prior experiences with public service processes and less familiarity with the associated challenges. People with less experience may view public services through a more idealistic lens, as they are less likely to encounter inefficiencies or setbacks in the service process.

On the other hand, individuals with more extensive work experience may be more critical and discerning, especially if they have had more exposure to the bureaucratic challenges or inefficiencies that can arise in government services. This could explain the relatively lower satisfaction ratings among respondents with 1-10 years of experience.

Table 20. Post-hoc analysis in the level of satisfaction in the implementation of the BFP services among the work experience of respondents along the public assistance desk.

Grp	Med	Grp	Med	Sig.
1-5 years	3.53	6-10 years	3.55	0.239
		More than 10 years	3.63	0.010*
		Less than 1 year	3.58	0.004*
6-10 years	3.55	More than 10 years	3.63	0.133
		Less than 1 year	3.58	0.074
More than 10 years	3.63	Less than 1 year	3.58	0.819

*Significant @ ≤ 0.05

Table 20 presents the post-hoc analysis in the level of satisfaction in the implementation of the BFP services among the years of work experience of respondents along the public assistance desk.

Comparing the level of satisfaction of those who have worked for 1-5 years (3.53) with those who worked for more than 10 years (3.63) and those who worked less than 1 year (3.58), the p-value of 0.010 and 0.004 respectively indicates that the difference is significant. These findings suggest that respondents with longer work experience tend to have a more positive view of the public assistance desk compared to those with less experience. One possible reason for the higher satisfaction among respondents with more than 10 years of work experience is the increased familiarity and perspective they have gained over time. With longer experience, individuals often develop a deeper understanding of how public service systems operate, and they are more likely to appreciate the efficiency, professionalism, and effectiveness of services like the public assistance desk. Individuals with extensive work experience are more attuned to the challenges that government services face and are often more appreciative when these services meet or exceed their expectations. Not only that, but experienced professionals tend to be more critical, but they also recognize the nuances of service delivery and are more likely to understand the complexities involved in the provision of public services.

Furthermore, respondents with over 10 years of work experience may have encountered significant improvements in the quality of public services over time. They may compare current experiences with those from earlier years and appreciate the progress made in terms of efficiency, customer service, and responsiveness. Research indicates that individuals who have worked in or around public service environments tend to become more patient and understanding of delays or challenges, which can lead to higher satisfaction when services meet current standards.

The significant difference in satisfaction between the "More than 10 Years" group and the "Less than 1 Year" and "1-5 Years" groups may also reflect differing expectations. Long-term employees or respondents with extensive work experience likely have a broader perspective on the strengths and weaknesses of public service operations. They may have higher expectations for responsiveness and professionalism, but when these expectations are met, they tend to report higher satisfaction, as they recognize the continuous improvements made over time.

Table 21. Comparative analysis in the level of satisfaction in the implementation of the BFP services among the highest educational attainment of respondents.

BFP services	Highest educational attainment								Kruskal-Wallis H-value	Test statistics p-value
	Elementary		High school		College		Postgraduate			
	Md	Int	Md	Int	Md	Int	Md	Int		
Acceptance and denial of applications of fire safety certificates	3.60	VS	3.59	VS	3.59	VS	3.45	VS	3.506	0.320
Issuance of fire safety certificates	3.50	VS	3.57	VS	3.54	VS	3.62	VS	1.997	0.573
Public assistance desk	3.50	VS	3.48	VS	3.53	VS	3.53	VS	0.683	0.877
Business one-stop shop (BOSS)	3.54	VS	3.53	VS	3.53	VS	3.42	VS	2.585	0.460

*Significant @ ≤ 0.05 ; Legend: VS: Very satisfied, S: Satisfied, D: Dissatisfied, VD: Very dissatisfied

Table 21 presents the comparative analysis of the level of satisfaction in the implementation of BFP services among respondents with varying levels of educational attainment. The results reveal that all educational groups—elementary, high school, college, and postgraduate—reported "Very Satisfied" (VS) ratings across all BFP service. This suggests that the BFP services are broadly well-received by respondents, irrespective of their educational background. Furthermore, the Kruskal-Wallis test shows no significant differences in satisfaction levels across the different educational groups, as all p-values are greater than 0.05. This indicates that educational attainment does not significantly influence satisfaction with BFP services, and satisfaction is largely consistent across the groups.

One possible explanation for this uniform satisfaction is that fire safety services, which include the processing of fire safety certificates and assistance provided by the BFP, are universally essential. Regardless of educational level, all individuals benefit from and recognize the importance of these services for public safety. Studies have shown that when public services are perceived as critical and universally applicable, such as fire safety measures, satisfaction tends to be high across diverse demographic groups. Additionally, the BFP likely employs standardized procedures for delivering services, ensuring that individuals from all educational backgrounds experience similar levels of service. This consistency in service delivery helps ensure that everyone, regardless of their education, perceives the BFP as an effective and accessible agency.

Moreover, professionalism and responsiveness from BFP staff play a crucial role in public satisfaction. The public assistance desk and BOSS are service-oriented platforms where professionalism, timely responses, and efficiency are paramount. Professionalism in public service is universally appreciated, regardless of educational background. The results indicate that both high school graduates and individuals with postgraduate education equally appreciate the professionalism and accessibility of BFP services, contributing to the overall high satisfaction ratings.

In conclusion, the findings suggest that the BFP's services are perceived positively by individuals from all educational backgrounds. The lack of significant differences in satisfaction levels emphasizes the effectiveness of the BFP's approach in delivering services that meet the needs of a diverse community. This highlights the importance of maintaining accessibility, efficiency, and professionalism in public services to ensure that they are beneficial for all citizens, regardless of their educational level. The BFP can continue to enhance its services by focusing on transparency, reducing bureaucracy, and maintaining consistent, high-quality service delivery across all demographics.

Action Plan Proposed to Enhance the Program and Service Implementation at the BFP

Below is the operational plan proposed by the researcher based on the findings of the study (Table 22).

The Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP) acts as a primary agency for public safety and disaster preparedness through its core functions (conducting fire safety inspections, responding to fires, providing emergency medical services, and conducting disaster risk reduction). The study "Assessing the Community Satisfaction with the Services and Programs of General Mariano Alvarez Fire Station" revealed that both BFP personnel and the majority of community members generally reported high satisfaction with BFP services, noting professionalism, effective communications, and efficient processes. These positive impressions validate the agency's ongoing public service and public safety commitment.

Despite these accomplishments, the study also uncovered several areas that warrant focused improvement. Among these are the limited frequency and impact of disaster preparedness drills, varying satisfaction levels among different demographic and experience groups, and the need for clearer guidelines in business application processes through the business one-stop shop (BOSS). Furthermore, while inclusivity has improved, there remain gender-based differences in satisfaction, particularly in firefighting operations, suggesting a need to further understand and address the unique expectations and experiences of diverse individuals.

Since the BFP plays a vital role in community protection and emergency response, intervention should focus on modifying and strengthening all levels of its programs and services to effectively respond to emerging public needs, and this action plan seeks to address these specific areas of improvement, promote inclusiveness, enhance internal operations, and strengthen community engagement. By prioritizing these initiatives, the BFP can further enhance service quality, build public trust, and contribute to creating more resilient and safer communities.

Table 22. Action plan.

Key results area	Key performance indicator	Innovative action plan	Persons responsible	Timeline	Resources needed	Means of verification	Quality objectives deployment
KRA 1: Efficient and effective governance, management, and leadership							
Disaster preparedness	Continuity and quality of regular drills (quarterly)	<p>Institutionalize quarterly eco-efficient disaster preparedness drills through updated SOPs and partnerships.</p> <p>Integrate disaster preparedness into barangay development plans to ensure long-term sustainability.</p> <p>Conduct training of trainers (TOT) to ensure continuity of local disaster response trainers.</p>	BFP personnel, LGUs, Barangay officials	Quarterly	SOP manuals, updated schedules	Drill schedules, institutional reports	Q1
Business process improvement	Sustained user satisfaction in BOSS transactions	<p>Maintain and enhance the simplified BOSS guidelines and expand digital access</p> <p>Develop user-friendly infographics and multilingual help desks for BOSS services.</p> <p>Incentivize online submissions by fast-tracking digitally complete applications</p>	BFP personnel, public affairs office	Q2 FY 2025 and ongoing	Digital infrastructure, staff orientation	Guidelines review, online traffic reports	Q2
Customer service	Ongoing improvement in client service ratings	<p>Continue periodic customer service training and mentoring for public assistance desk personnel</p> <p>Establish a rotation system</p>	BFP personnel	Q3 FY 2025 and annually	Training materials, feedback tools	Training logs, satisfaction survey results	Q3

		<p>allowing personnel to shadow top-rated desk officers for benchmarking.</p> <p>Create a mobile help desk unit for outreach in far-flung barangays.</p>					
Public education	Sustained information dissemination	<p>Continue and expand the 'Know Your BFP Services' campaign through digital and barangay-based initiatives.</p> <p>Launch a quarterly webinar series on fire prevention and safety for schools and workplaces.</p> <p>Collaborate with local media for weekly "fire safety tips" radio segments.</p>	BFP public information unit, Barangay councils	Q2 2025 and ongoing	Digital flyers, presentations	Distribution logs, public awareness surveys	Q4
Community engagement	Continued community participation	<p>Institutionalize community fire safety booths as a regular feature in local events.</p> <p>Train barangay youth leaders as peer fire safety ambassadors.</p> <p>Create annual barangay-level fire safety contests to drive engagement</p>	BFP officers, Barangay councils, youth volunteers	During local festivities and events	Booth kits, volunteer coordination tools	Activity reports, signup sheets	Q5

Summary of Findings, Conclusions, and Recommendations

Summary of Findings

The findings reveal a high level of satisfaction among both residents and Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP) personnel regarding the implementation of BFP programs across various areas, including fire safety enforcement, firefighting operations, emergency medical services (EMS), and disaster management. Both groups expressed satisfaction with the clarity and effectiveness of fire safety programs, the adequacy of firefighting equipment, and the reliability of EMS, highlighting the BFP's internal commitment to safety and effective emergency response. Additionally, the BFP's visible community presence and collaborative efforts with other agencies foster trust and enhance disaster preparedness. However, the lower satisfaction ratings for the frequency and effectiveness of disaster preparedness drills indicate a need for more consistent training and evaluation to improve community resilience.

Moreover, findings indicate that all demographic groups, including age, gender, civil status, work experience, and educational attainment, reported a "Very Satisfied" rating regarding the implementation of Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP) programs, suggesting a broadly positive perception of fire safety enforcement, firefighting operations, emergency medical services, and disaster management. The Kruskal-Wallis test results further revealed no significant differences in satisfaction levels based on age, civil status, work experience, or educational attainment, highlighting BFP's equitable and standardized approach in service delivery. However, a statistically significant difference was observed in satisfaction levels concerning firefighting operations among gender groups, with individuals identifying as "Other" reporting the highest satisfaction. This variation may stem from differing gender-based expectations of emergency services and perceptions of inclusivity. Overall, the findings underscore the effectiveness of the BFP's structured programs, community engagement, and public awareness initiatives in maintaining consistently high satisfaction levels across diverse demographic profiles.

In terms of the implementation of BFP services, findings indicate that both residents and BFP personnel are highly satisfied, including the acceptance and denial of fire safety certificate applications, the issuance process, the public assistance desk, and the business one-stop shop (BOSS). The results reveal that clear communication, efficient procedures, professional and approachable staff, and transparent processes contribute to consistently high satisfaction levels across all indicators. While no significant concerns were found, the study highlights areas for potential improvement, such as enhancing the clarity of guidelines for business application requirements at the BOSS.

Furthermore, the findings reveal that respondents across all demographic groups-including age, gender, civil status, work experience, and educational attainment-reported high levels of satisfaction with the implementation of BFP services, such as the acceptance and denial of applications of fire safety certificates, issuance of fire safety certificates, public assistance desk, and business one-stop shop (BOSS). The Kruskal-Wallis test results indicate no significant differences in satisfaction levels based on age, gender, civil status, or educational attainment, suggesting that BFP services are perceived as equitable, efficient, and universally essential. However, a significant difference was observed in satisfaction with the public assistance desk across work experience groups, with respondents having less than one year or more than ten years of experience reporting higher satisfaction levels than those with intermediate work experience. These findings suggest that BFP services are effectively meeting public needs through standardized processes, professionalism, and accessibility, reinforcing the importance of maintaining transparency and efficiency in service delivery to sustain high satisfaction levels across diverse demographic groups.

Conclusion

The study concludes that the Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP) has successfully implemented its programs and services, with consistently high satisfaction ratings among both residents and BFP personnel across various demographic groups.

The findings highlight the effectiveness of fire safety enforcement, firefighting operations, emergency medical services, and disaster management, demonstrating the BFP's commitment to public safety through clear communication, standardized procedures, and professional service delivery.

Although there were no significant differences observed in the satisfaction levels in terms of age, gender, civil status, or educational attainment, variations in satisfaction with specific services, such as the public assistance desk and firefighting operations, suggest areas for targeted improvements. Enhancing disaster preparedness drills, refining business application processes at the business one-stop shop (BOSS), and

further promoting inclusivity in emergency response efforts can help sustain and enhance public trust in the BFP. Ultimately, maintaining transparency, efficiency, and accessibility will be key to continuously improving service delivery and ensuring community safety and resilience.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following are recommended.

- ☞ The Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP) should enhance the frequency and effectiveness of disaster preparedness drills to improve community resilience and ensure both residents and personnel are well-prepared for emergencies.
- ☞ The BFP should improve the clarity of business application guidelines at the business one-stop shop (BOSS) to streamline the process and provide clearer instructions for applicants.
- ☞ The BFP should optimize the operations of the public assistance desk by addressing the variations in satisfaction among different work experience groups to ensure consistent and high-quality service for all users.
- ☞ The BFP should strengthen community engagement and awareness campaigns to reinforce public trust and encourage active participation in fire safety and disaster preparedness programs.
- ☞ The BFP should sustain transparency and efficiency in service delivery by maintaining standardized procedures, professionalism, and accessibility while establishing regular feedback mechanisms to address emerging concerns proactively.
- ☞ Conduct further studies on gender-based differences in satisfaction levels regarding firefighting operations and implement measures to promote inclusivity and equitable service delivery.

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